

3. J. S. KENNEDY, *Bull. Entomol. Res.*, 1947, **37**, 593.
4. L. N. MUKHERJEE and S. D. SHUKLA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1971, **48**, 123.
5. L. N. MUKHERJEE and S. D. SHUKLA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **42**, 805.
6. L. N. MUKHERJEE and S. D. SHUKLA, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1965, **28**, 177; 1967, **30**, 187.
7. S. D. SHUKLA and KRANTI KUMAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, **58**, 726.
8. S. D. SHUKLA and KRANTI KUMAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, (in press).
9. S. U. PICKERING, Emulsions, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, 91, 2001.
10. W. W. YOTHEBS and J. R. WINSTON, *Agr. Research.*, 1925, **31**, 59.

Metal Chelates of Lanthanoids. A Spectrophotometric study using Bromopyrogallol Red as a Ligand

MOHAN S. JOG*, SUBHASH C. PANDE**, VASANT L. SHAH† & SATENDRA P. SANGAL‡

Laxminarayan Institute of Technology, Nagpur

Manuscript received 14 May 1974; accepted 20 August 1974

BROMOPYROGALLOL Red (abbrev. BPGR) has been observed to possess very interesting chromogenic properties. It forms coloured chelates with a number of metal ions¹. Aluminium, gallium and indium form a 1 : 2 (metal : ligand) complex² while titanium, zirconium and hafnium form a 1 : 1 chelate with this reagent³. Thorium and uranium⁴, molybdenum and tungsten⁵ also form 1 : 1 chelate with this reagent. Herrington and Steed⁶ have used the reagent in the determination of rare-earths while Suk⁷ reported the determination of lanthanum under similar conditions. It was thought to be of interest to study the chelates of BPGR with Sc, Y, La, Ce, Pr, Nd, Sm, Eu, Gd, Tb, Dy, Ho and Er. In the present communication, the results on the composition, formation constants and other characteristics of the chelates formed between BPGR and the metals mentioned above are reported.

Experimental

Instruments : Hydrogen ion concentration of the solutions was adjusted by using a Leeds and Northrup pH meter with a glass calomel electrode of the same make. The pH meter was standardized by standard buffers supplied along with the instrument. For spectro-photometric studies a Beckman model B spectrophotometer operated on 115 V/50 cycles AC mains was used. 10 mm thickness matched glass cells were used for solutions.

Conditions of experiment : All experiments were carried out in a thermostatically controlled air conditioned room maintained at $25^{\circ} \pm 1^{\circ}$.

Chemicals : Solutions of Bromopyrogallol Red were prepared by dissolving suitable amounts of the reagent in 40% alcohol and the final volume was

made up with double distilled water. Solutions of rare-earths were prepared by dissolving the requisite amounts of the metal oxides or chlorides in minimum quantity of HCl and then making up the volume with double distilled water.

Results and Discussion

Effect of time and pH on an aqueous solution of BPGR :

Freshly prepared solutions were used. The colour of the dye varies with change in pH. The change in λ_{max} of the dye with variation in pH is shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1

EFFECT OF pH ON THE AQUEOUS SOLUTIONS OF BPGR

pH	Wavelength of maximum absorbance (nm)
0.1—0.05	480
0.5—3.2	430
3.2—4.5	570
4.5—8.0	580

Effect of pH on the formation of the chelates :

The chelates of the metal ions studied with BPGR are formed within a limited range of pH. The results are included in Table 2.

TABLE 2

EFFECT OF pH ON THE FORMATION OF CHELATES

Chelate	pH range of stability	λ_{max} of Chelate (nm)
Sc(III)-BPGR	3.3—6.0	590
Y(III)-BPGR	3.8—6.5	680
La(III)-BPGR	4.1—8.0	720
Ce(III)-BPGR	3.8—7.0	690
Pr(III)-BPGR	4.0—7.0	690
Nd(III)-BPGR	4.0—9.1	690
Sm(III)-BPGR	4.0—8.0	690
Eu(III)-BPGR	3.9—7.0	690
Gd(III)-BPGR	5.5—8.0	690
Tb(III)-BPGR	5.5—8.1	690
Dy(III)-BPGR	5.6—8.9	690
Ho(III)-BPGR	5.6—8.8	680
Er(III)-BPGR	5.0—8.5	680

The table indicates that study of all the elements can be made at pH 6.0.

Nature of the complexes formed :

Several mixtures containing metal ion and BPGR in the ratio 0 : 1, 1 : 0.5, 1 : 1, 1 : 2, and 1 : 3 were prepared by keeping the total volume 25 ml in each case. After mixing the metal solution with BPGR solution at the same pH, it was observed that the pH falls. Hence 5.0 ml of sodium acetate-acetic buffer was added to maintain the required pH. Absorbance readings were noted between

*V.R.C.E., Nagpur, **G.S.I., Nagpur, †Pratap College, Amalner, ‡L.I.T., Nagpur.

NOTES

500 nm, 700 nm at 10 nm, 20 nm or 25 nm intervals. The results are shown in Table 2.

Composition of the chelates :

The composition of the metal chelates have been determined spectrophotometrically using the method of continuous variations⁸ and the mole ratio method⁹. In all the systems studied the composition has been found to be 1 : 1 (metal : ligand). The results of composition are also included in Table 3.

Evaluation of stability constants :

The conditional stability constants have been determined by the method of Dey¹⁰ *et al* and the mole ratio method at 25° and at pH of study. The results are included in Table 3.

TABLE 3

COMPOSITION AND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF BPGR CHELATES

Chelation system	Composition Metal : BPGR	log k	Method
Sc(III)-BPGR	1 : 1	5.4	(i)
		6.6	(ii)
Y(III)-BPGR	"	5.9	(i)
		6.9	(ii)
La(III)-BPGR	"	5.3	(i)
		6.6	(ii)
Ce(III)-BPGR	"	5.2	(i)
		5.5	(ii)
Pr(III)-BPGR	"	5.1	(i)
		5.8	(ii)
Nd(III)-BPGR	"	5.1	(i)
		6.1	(ii)
Sm(III)-BPGR	"	5.0	(i)
		5.8	(ii)
Eu(III)-BPGR	"	4.5	(i)
		5.9	(ii)
Gd(III)-BPGR	"	5.2	(i)
		6.8	(ii)
Tb(III)-BPGR	"	4.3	(i)
		6.5	(ii)
Dy(III)-BPGR	"	4.2	(i)
		5.2	(ii)
Ho(III)-BPGR	"	4.2	(i)
		6.2	(ii)
Er(III)-BPGR	"	4.2	(i)
		6.4	(ii)

(i) Method of Dey *et al.* (ii) Mole Ratio method.

References

1. S. C. PANDE and S. P. SANGAL, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1969, 311, 328.
2. S. C. PANDE and S. P. SANGAL, *Chim. Analyt.*, 1969, 51, 555.
3. S. C. PANDE and S. P. SANGAL, *Microchem. J.* (in press).
4. S. C. PANDE and S. P. SANGAL, *Microchem. J.*, 1968, 13, 674.
5. S. C. PANDE and S. P. SANGAL, *Chim. Analyt.* (in press).

6. J. HERRINGTON and K. L. STEED, *Anal. Chim. Acta.*, 1960, 22, 180.
7. V. SUK, *Coll. Czech. Chem. Comm.*, 1966, 31, 387.
8. P. JOB, *Compt. rend.*, 1925, 180, 928; *Ann. Chim.*, 1928, 9, 113.
9. J. H. JONES and A. L. JONES, *Ind. Engg. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1944, 16, 111.
10. A. K. MUKHERJI and A. K. DEV, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1958, 6, 314.

Chalcones. XV : Potential Germicides Derived from 2-Methoxy-1-Acetonaphthone

SHYAM SUNDER MISRA*

Department of Chemistry, H. B. Technological Institute, Kanpur

Manuscript received 29 January 1972; revised 7 August 1974; accepted 13 August 1974

AMONG the different fields of study in Chalcone Chemistry, their aspect of antimicrobial property was most fascinating to modern chemists. As early in 1948, Schraufstatter¹⁻² showed the path, that chalcones are capable of destroying disease germs. Later researches proved³⁻⁷ that these compounds having different substituents *viz.*, hydroxy, methoxy, chloro, bromo, etc. either in ketone part or aldehyde were found to possess bacteriostatic, anthelmintic, fungicidal, carcinogenic, cardiovascular, etc. activity. Moreover, Wilson and coworkers⁸ have observed that methoxy chalcones can check up the destruction of adrenaline. It may be due to the fact that ethylenic linkage has the property to react with certain cellular constituents. This has prompted the present author to synthesize methoxy chalcone analogues.

The present investigation is an attempt to synthesize methoxy naphthalene chalcone analogues by Claisen-Schmidt condensation and to study their antimicrobial activity against gram positive bacteria (*S. aureus*), gram negative bacteria (*E. coli*) and *A. niger* by agar-cup method.

In order to achieve this end 2-methoxy-1-acetonaphthone was condensed with different benzaldehydes in presence of alcoholic potassium hydroxide solution (Table 1). The identity of the compounds was established by preparing a few 2,4-dinitrophenyl hydrazone derivatives, colour reaction with concentrated H₂SO₄ and elemental analyses.

The germicidal and fungicidal activity was tested by agar-cup method at a concentration of 100±10 µg/ml. against *S. aureus*, *E. coli* and *A. niger* and compared with benzoic acid. The inocula were prepared from stationary culture and inhibition of growth was checked at an incubation temperature of (32°±2°) after 24 hrs. No encouraging results were obtained.

* Present Address, Department of Chemistry, Feroze Gandhi Post-Graduate College, Rae-Bareilly-229001.